

Cognition in early-stage neuronal alpha-synuclein disease with hyposmia

**Parkinson's
Progression
Markers
Initiative**

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BACKGROUND / RATIONALE

► Long-term significant cognitive impairment is a common and feared outcome in Parkinson's disease (PD), with dementia affecting up to 80% of patients long-term. Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) is also relatively common³, even in de novo or early disease. In addition, subtle cognitive changes can be detected in the prodromal state, including in patients with isolated REM sleep behavior disorder (iRBD) or persons with hyposmia.

► Recently a biological definition and staging system intended for research use was proposed for neuronal α -synuclein disease (NSD). NSD is defined by the presence of pathological neuronal- α syn species detected in vivo as the primary biological anchor, with those individuals subsequently at risk for dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction, which is the secondary biological anchor. This biological definition also incorporates a staging system, the neuronal α -synuclein disease integrated staging system (NSD-ISS), rooted in the aforementioned biological anchors and the degree of functional impairment caused by clinical signs or symptoms. The presence of clinical manifestations marks the transition to stage 2 and beyond, with Stage 2 characterized by subtle signs or symptoms (e.g., hyposmia or iRBD, or subtle motor or cognitive symptoms) but without functional impairment (i.e., prodromal disease). Stage 2A is neuronal- α syn positive but dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction negative, while Stage 2B is neuronal- α syn positive and dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction positive. In the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) study, data from which led to the proposal for the NSD-ISS, neuronal- α syn is determined by a CSF α syn seed amplification assay (SAA) test, and dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction by a SPECT dopamine transporter (DAT) scan.

► When assessing cognitive abilities in a detailed fashion, an option that allows one to combine the richness and details of a neuropsychological battery with the simplicity of a single test score is to create a cognitive summary score (CSS) after all detailed test results are normed on the same scale (e.g., z-score). The PPMI study originally had a PD-MCI Level I battery (five detailed, well-established cognitive tests) with published norms. We recently implemented a robust norming process using baseline PPMI data to increase sensitivity to detect cognitive differences in PD compared with healthy controls (HCs).

► The goals of these analyses were to use the new NSD-ISS to assess cognition in persons with hyposmia, a prodromal PD symptom, and Stage 2 NSD. We hypothesized that hyposmics with early-stage NSD would be associated with worse cognitive performance compared with HCs, and that comorbid iRRB and dopaminergic deficits would be increase the severity of cognitive deficits.

STUDY DESIGN

► **Participants:** The PPMI study and cohort has been extensively described^{15,16}. All participants signed an approved informed consent form. Inclusion criteria for PD participants included: (1) an asymmetric resting tremor or asymmetric bradykinesia, or at least two symptoms out of resting tremor, bradykinesia, and rigidity; (2) a recent clinical diagnosis of PD (mean [SD] duration from diagnosis = 8.5 [7.3] months); (3) being untreated with PD medications; (4) evidence of dopaminergic deficit based on DAT SPECT imaging; and (5) being non-demented. For the purposes of these analyses HCs were required to (1) not have clinically significant neurological dysfunction, (2) not have a first-degree relative with PD (3) have a Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) score ≥ 27 , (4) not have hyposmia and (5) have a negative α -syn SAA test.

► **Redefining PD participants using NSD-ISS:** All the aforementioned cohorts were reclassified from their enrollment cohort to the NSD-ISS. All NSD participants were required to have hyposmia, positive α -syn seed amplification assay (SAA) test, and either with or without dopaminergic dysfunction. The presence of clinical manifestations marks the transition to stage 2 and beyond, with Stage 2 characterized by subtle signs or symptoms (e.g., hyposmia or iRBD, or subtle motor or cognitive symptoms) but without functional impairment (i.e., prodromal disease). Stage 2A is neuronal- α syn positive but dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction negative, while Stage 2B is neuronal- α syn positive and dopaminergic neuronal dysfunction positive.

► **Cognitive summary score:** Baseline data were used, at which point PD participants were recently diagnosed and had not yet begun treatment with PD medication. The following steps were taken: (1) creating a robust HC subgroup that did not demonstrate cognitive decline over time; (2) using the robust HC subgroup to create regression-based internally-derived standardized scores (z-scores) for six cognitive scores across five tests; and (3) creating a CSS by averaging all standardized test z-scores. The original cognitive battery was used to create the CSS to optimize the amount of data available for analyses. This original battery was composed of the Hopkins Verbal Learning Test-Revised (HLVT-R immediate and delayed free recall scores)(²⁴), the Benton Judgment of Line Orientation - 15 item version (JLO)(²⁵), Symbol-Digit Modalities Test (SDMT)(²⁶), Letter-Number Sequencing (LNS)(²⁷), and semantic (animal) fluency(²⁸). Together these tests assess memory, visuospatial function, information processing speed, executive function, working memory and language. Global cognition was assessed with the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)¹⁷.

STUDY DESIGN (CONT'D)

► Analyses:

Statistical analyses were performed using SAS v9.4 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC; sas.com; RRID:SCR_008567). Using PPMI baseline data, participant characteristics were compared between the Stage 2A, Stage 2B and HC groups using mean (standard deviation) and median (interquartile range) for continuous measures and frequency (percentage) for categorical measures. Next, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was performed to assess the difference between mean CSS for the three groups. This was followed by post hoc analyses to evaluate pairwise comparisons using Tukey's Honestly Significant Differences (HSD) Test; Cohen's d effect sizes were also evaluated and used to compare the three subgroups.

To evaluate the impact of superimposed RBD (in addition to hyposmia) on cognitive performance in Stage 2 participants, two-sample t tests were performed to compare the CSS between hyposmic only vs. comorbid hyposmic + RBD participants. The associated Cohen's d effect sizes were also evaluated and reported. This analysis was performed for the overall Stage 2 group, as well as based on their dopaminergic dysfunction status (i.e., separately within Stage 2A and Stage 2B subgroups only).

For the 132 participants with iRBD, 106 (80%) were PSG-confirmed whereas 26 (20%) were not.

RESULTS

Table 1. Participant characteristics

► Stage 2 older than HCs (but CSS controls for age)

► Stage 2 more likely to meet cognitive criteria for Stage 2 than HCs, but still <20% did

► Stage 2 more likely to meet motor criteria for Stage 2 than HCs, particularly Stage 2B

► Almost half of Stage 2B participants were enrolled as iPD

Variable	Subgroup		
	HC* (N = 158)	Stage 2A (N = 175)	Stage 2B (N = 318)
Sex (male), n (%)	96 (61%)	111 (63%)	204 (64%)
Age at baseline, mean (SD)	59.0 (11.7)	67.9 (5.8)	65.3 (8.1)
Median (IQR)	60.4 (53.0, 67.0)	67.8 (63.8, 71.2)	65.8 (61.0, 70.8)
Meets cognitive criteria for stage 2, n (%)			
Item 1.1 = 1 AND MoCA ≥ 25	13 (8%)	32 (18%)	60 (19%)
Not evaluable	1	0	0
Meets motor criteria for stage 2, n (%)			
Subthreshold parkinsonism OR PD meds	5 (3%)	42 (24%)	184 (58%)
Not evaluable	1	0	0
Meets non-motor criteria for stage 2, n (%)			
Hyposmia OR RBD	18 (11%)	175 (100%)	318 (100%)
Not evaluable	1	0	0
Non-motor subgroup, n (%)			
Hyposmia AND RBD	0	68 (39%)	64 (20%)
Hyposmia only	18 (11%)	107 (61%)	254 (80%)
Neither	139 (89%)	0	0
Not evaluable	1	0	0
Cohort/subgroup at enrollment, n (%)			
HC	158 (100%)	10 (6%)	2 (1%)
sPD	0	5 (3%)	141 (44%)
Genetic PD	0	0	16 (5%)
iRBD	0	68 (39%)	64 (20%)
Hyposmia	0	83 (47%)	92 (29%)
Genetic NMC	0	7 (4%)	2 (1%)
SWEDD	0	2 (1%)	1 (<1%)

RESULTS

Table 2. Cognitive scores by subgroup

► Stage 2A < SHC (z-score mean difference =0.10, p-value NS; effect size=0.16)

► Stage 2B < SHC (z-score mean difference =0.26, p-value <0.05; effect size=0.40)

► Stage 2B < Stage 2A (z-score mean difference =0.15, p-value <0.05)

Variable	Subgroup		
	HC (N = 158)	Stage 2A (N = 175)	Stage 2B (N = 318)
MoCA, mean (SD)	28.3 (1.1)	26.9 (2.3)	27.1 (2.3)
Median (IQR)	28 (27, 29)	27 (25, 29)	28 (26, 29)
Cognitive summary score mean (SD)	-0.02 (0.61)	-0.12 (0.69)	-0.27 (0.66)
Median (IQR)	-0.03 (-0.46, 0.40)	-0.13 (-0.61, 0.39)	-0.25 (-0.69, 0.22)

Table 3. Cognitive scores by RBD status for NSD Stage 2

► Ignoring dopamine dysfunction status, SAA+ hyposmia has cognitive deficits, with superimposed RBD doubling the magnitude (z-score mean difference =0.19, p-value <0.05, effect size =0.28)

► In participants without dopamine dysfunction, hyposmia has normal cognition, and addition of comorbid RBD drives the cognitive impairment (z-score mean difference =0.33, p-value <0.05, effect size =0.49)

► In participants with dopamine dysfunction, hyposmia has impaired cognition, and comorbid RBD has additive effect, but not statistically significant (z-score mean difference =0.15, p-value =0.10, effect size =0.23)

Variable	Entire Stage 2 group	
	Hyposmic only (N = 361)	Hyposmic + RBD (N = 132)
Cognitive summary score, mean (SD)	-0.17 (0.66)	-0.35 (0.69)
Median (IQR)	-0.17 (-0.64, 0.32)	-0.35 (-0.82, 0.10)
Stage 2A subgroup		
Hyposmic only (N = 107)		
Hyposmic + RBD (N = 68)		
Cognitive summary score, mean (SD)	0.01 (0.68)	-0.32 (0.66)
Median (IQR)	0.02 (-0.54, 0.48)	-0.33 (-0.77, 0.06)
Stage 2B subgroup		
Hyposmic only (N = 254)		
Hyposmic + RBD (N = 64)		
Cognitive summary score, mean (SD)	-0.24 (0.64)	-0.39 (0.72)
Median (IQR)	-0.22 (-0.67, 0.24)	-0.38 (-0.84, 0.13)

CONCLUSIONS

► Hyposmia with early-stage NSD is associated with detectable cognitive deficits compared with SHC, particularly when dopamine system impairment is superimposed

► Hyposmia alone not associated with cognitive deficits unless dopaminergic deficit superimposed

► RBD superimposed on hyposmia significantly worsens cognition, even when dopaminergic deficits not present

► Preliminary results support the inclusion in NSD-ISS of a cognitive domain for symptom progression and functional impairment in early disease stages

► Future research ideas:

- Examine cognitive decline longitudinally in Stage 2
- Test cognition in those meeting cognitive vs. motor vs. non-motor subgroups
- Compare cognitive summary score with individual cognitive tests (z-scores)
- Utilize expanded cognitive battery once prepared
- Examine association with self-reported cognitive change and PDAQ-15
- Neurobiological correlates (DAT scan mean striatum SBR, serum/CSF NfL, polygenic risk score, AD panel (A β 42, tau, A β 42:40 ratio, total tau, p-tau, tau:A β 42, ApoE4), SAA kinetic parameters)

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PPMI data downloaded from PPMI website: <http://www.ppmi-info.org/>

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